

Emergency Treatment of Ruptured Aneurysms on Arteriovenous Fistulas in Dialysis Patients

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Aneurysm ruptures in arteriovenous fistulas are rare complications of hemodialysis vascular access. These are serious surgical emergencies that can endanger the patient's vital prognosis.

Objective: The main objective of this study is to evaluate the epidemiological profile of this surgical emergency and to analyze the results of surgery.

Patients and methods: This retrospective study includes all consecutive files of patients in the cardiovascular surgery department of Gafsa hospital between January 1, 2019 and June 30, 2023 for the management of a rupture of an aneurysm on arteriovenous fistulas. Single bleeding from the puncture site of the arteriovenous fistula without was excluded. **Results:** A total of 36 patients (25 women (50.6%) and 11 men (49.4%)) were admitted for rupture of an aneurysm due to arteriovenous fistula. The average age of the subjects was 53.4 ± 12.7 years. The humerocephalic fistula was the first location of aneurysm ruptures (58.3%). The average age of these arteriovenous fistulas at the time of aneurysm rupture was 4.52 ± 1.67 years. Exclusion of AVF with flattening of the aneurysm was the most practiced technique (94.4%).

Conclusion: Rupture of aneurysms in arteriovenous fistulas in hemodialysis patients is the most serious complication. Exclusion of the arteriovenous fistula and aneurysmorrhaphy constitute the surgical options in an emergency context.

Keywords: Arteriovenous fistula; Aneurysm; Surgery; Aneurysmorrhaphy

INTRODUCTION

Arteriovenous fistula (AVF) is the long-term hemodialysis procedure of choice in patients with chronic kidney disease.^[1,2] AVF aneurysms are secondary to repeated perforations which can weaken the vein wall in some patients. Its incidence is approximately 5 to 6%.^[3] These patients may present with a large and painful aneurysm sac that may lead to necrosis of the dermal tissue. It may become infected due to vascular access or traumatic events. The aneurysm sac may rupture, leading to possible fatal hemorrhage. This complication can be treated by several techniques such as surgical ligation and resection, stents and perivascular wire mesh.^[4,5]

The aim of this study was to evaluate the epidemiological profile of patients operated for rupture of aneurysm on AVF and to evaluate the effectiveness of different therapeutic modalities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This is a retrospective study extended over a period of 4 years, between January 2019 and June 2022, about 36 patients presenting with an aneurysm rupture due to arteriovenous fistula, and having been treated within the department of cardiovascular surgery at the Gafsa regional hospital.

All data used in our work were collected from the patient files of the cardiovascular surgery department of the Gafsa regional hospital.

The collection of data in medical files was done in ascending chronological order from January 2019 to June 2023, using operating sheets.

For the statistical study, we reported all the data on an Excel table and we used the SPSS 23 software.

The qualitative variables of our study were expressed as percentages and numbers, while the quantitative variables were expressed as means \pm standard deviations.

RÉSULT

We operated on 36 patients during the period from January 2014 to December 2022. The average age of our patients was 53.4 ± 12.7 years. We identified in this study 11 men and 25 women.

The reasons for consultation were:

- Bleeding with thinning of the skin near the aneurysm in 23 patients (64%) (Figure 1).
- Bleeding with necrosis of the skin near the aneurysm in 7 patients (19.5%) (Figure 2).
- Bleeding with the presence of pus and inflammatory signs near the aneurysm in 4 patients (11%) (Figure 3).
- Rupture of the aneurysm under the skin in 2 patients (5.5%) (Figure 4).

Figure 1: Aneurysm on a radial AVF with wall thinning

Figure 2: Aneurysm on a humerocephalic AVF with wall necrosis

Figure 3: Aneurysm on a humerocephalic AVF with stigmata of infection

Figure 4: Aneurysm on a humerocephalic AVF with rupture under the skin

Two patients (5.6%) had an arteriovenous fistula in the right arm against 34 (94.4%) who had a arteriovenous fistula in the left arm. Twenty-one were humerocephalic fistulas (58.3%), seven (19.4%) were humerobasilic fistulas, six (16.7%) were radial fistulas while the last 2 (5.6 %) were humeroaxillary bypass with prosthesis (Table I).

We found that these arteriovenous fistulas had been created between one and a half and eleven years of age with an average of 4.52 ± 1.67 years (Table II).

All of our patients were treated surgically. Thirty-four patients (94.4%) had an AVF exclusion . The principle is to control the artery upstream and downstream of the anastomotic chamber, ligate the AVF and flatten the aneurysm (Figure 5).

Table I: Topographic distribution of aneurysms on AVF

Anatomical site	Type of AVF	Number	Percentage
Radial	AVF	6	16,7%
Left upper limb	Humerocephalic	AVF 20	55,6%
	Humero-basilic	AVF 6	16,7%
	Humeroaxillary	2 bypass	5,6%
Right upper limb	Humerocephalic	AVF 1	2,7%
	Humero-basilic	AVF 1	2,7%

Table II: Ages of different types of AVF

Type of AVF	Numbre	Age of AVF
Radial AVF	6	7 ±1,09
Humerocephalic AVF	21	4,26 ±1,2
Humero-basilic AVF	7	4,16± 0,69
Humeroaxillary bypass	2	1,25

Figure 5: Clamping of the artery upstream and downstream of the AVF

The second surgical technique used is the aneurysmorrhaphy (Figure 6). His principle of is to reduce the lumen of the aneurysmal vein to the diameter of the adjacent vein.

The skin incision was made all along the aneurysm, the dissection of the aneurysm extended to a level where the vein regains a normal diameter. A dose of heparin of 50 mg was administered intraoperatively. Then clamping was performed upstream and downstream of the anastomotic chamber. Caliber reduction was performed after excision of excess venous tissue, using a back and forth overlock with Prolene 5/0 in a calibrated manner on a suction probe. We performed this technique in 2 cases.

The postoperative course was simple for all patients. The mean length of hospital stay was 2.02 days with a maximum stay of 3 days. We did not collect any deaths in our series.

Figure 6: Reconstructive surgery for aneurysmorrhaphy of an aneurysmal arteriovenous fistula

DISCUSSION

In the study by Bakran et al regarding AVF aneurysms, they referred to segments of dilated vein, the diameter of which exceeds 1.5 to 2 times the diameter of the adjacent vein.^[6] Several types of aneurysms can develop, either on the arterial side, anastomotic, or along the drainage route. Some are true arterial or venous aneurysms, others are false aneurysms. The frequencies of AVF aneurysms reported in the literature vary from 0% to 17% for native AVF and from 0% to 7% for polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) bypass grafts.^[6,7] The treatment of aneurysms on the AVF is surgical, the action to be taken depends above all on the seat of the aneurysm in relation to the AVF, ranging from simple flattening with closure of the feeding orifice, to flattening with interposition of a graft.^[7] In our series, we performed 34 AVF exclusions and only 2 aneurysmorrhaphy due to the emergency context. This is explained by the fact that the patients who come to us for the creation of a fistula and dialysis come from a disadvantaged socio-economic background and often do not have regular follow-ups. We have also encountered patients who presented with a ruptured fistula and severe bleeding. Due to logistical difficulties, these patients do not arrive in time at the hospital.

Aneurysmal dilation on AVF is a slow process, this progressive risk increases with the age of creation of the vascular access.^[8] The time to appearance is reported in the literature between 1.2 and 4.4 years after the creation of the fistula.^[8-12]

In our study, the aneurysmal AVFs had a mean age of 4.52 ± 1.67 years.

Aneurysmorrhaphy represents a simple, effective technique allowing the cure of the aneurysm while preserving a functional approach and it represents the technique of choice proposed by several authors in the treatment of aneurysmal complications of AVF.^[13-19]

However, it is only indicated for some when the aneurysm is segmental, allowing the puncture of a healthy portion after reduction in size. In the event of an extensive aneurysm or multiple false aneurysms limiting the puncture area after aneurysmorrhaphy, a two-stage cure can be proposed in order to leave a puncture area and thus avoid having to resort to central venous catheters and their thrombotic complications.

In our study we performed this technique in two cases.

CONCLUSION

Rupture of aneurysms on arteriovenous fistulas is a very serious complication immediately involving the vital prognosis of patients who are already spontaneously anemic. Faced with this hemorrhage, the attitude is unequivocal, it consists of an emergency gesture of hemostasis.

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